

THE EDGE DETECTION FROM IMAGES CORRUPTED BY MIXED NOISE USING FUZZY RULES

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ABSTRACT

Pre-filtering is necessary before the edge detection when images corrupted by additive noise. However, this process degrades image details. In this paper, a new edge detection from images that corrupted by mixed noise is proposed. The proposed method is combined edge detection and noise reduction by fuzzy inference in order to extract image edges from noisy images, correctly.

1. INTRODUCTION

The edge detection is one of the basic and important process for the image processing. When we detect the edge from noisy images, it is necessary to reduce noises by pre-filtering. However, even if nonlinear filtering degrade the image edges and details.

We have already proposed the method of edge detection from images that corrupted by impulse noise[1]. This method is useful to detect image edges from images which are corrupted by impulse noise. However, this method dose not works well for images corrupted by non-impulse noise (e.g., Gaussian noise) or mixed noise.

In this paper, a novel method of edge detection from images that corrupted by mixed noise (i.e, Gaussian noise plus impulse noise) using fuzzy inference is proposed. The proposed method consists of two set of fuzzy rules. The aim of one set of fuzzy rules is the estimating of the number of impulse noise in the window. The aim of the other set of fuzzy rules is the detection of image edges from images corrupted by only Gaussian noise, on the assumption that the number of impulse noise in the window is known. Thus, the edge detection and mixed noise reduction are realized at the same time by the combining of the two fuzzy rules.

2. THE ALGORITHM

2.1 The definition of input images

this paper, images are assumed to be corrupted by mixed noise (i.e., Gaussian noise plus impulse noise). Thus, $P(i,j)=\{(i,j) | 1 \leq i \leq m ; 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ is input data which is given by

$$P(i,j) = \begin{cases} P_0(i,j) + g(i,j) & : \text{prob. } 1-p_1-p_2 \\ h & : \text{prob. } p_1 \cdots (1) \\ 0 & : \text{prob. } p_2 \end{cases}$$

where $P_0(i,j)$ is an original image and $g(i,j)$ is a zero mean Gaussian noise with variance σ_n^2 . $P(i,j)=h$ and $P(i,j)=0$ in Eq.(1) mean that (i,j) sample is corrupted by white and black impulse noises, respectively.

2.2 Estimation of the number of impulse noise

Let the $P(i,j)$ is the center pixel of the window with $M \times M$ ($N=M^2$) $P_{(k)}(i,j)$ is the k -th smallest data in the window (i.e., $P_{(1)}(i,j) \leq P_{(2)}(i,j) \leq \cdots \leq P_{(N-1)}(i,j) \leq P_{(N)}(i,j)$). Signal edge is able to detect by subtracting $P_{(1)}(i,j)$ from $P_{(n)}(i,j)$ which is correspond to the morphological gradient [2] (the following, this edge detection method is called Max.-Min. method). However, impulse noise exists in the window, around max. data and min. data are suspected impulse noise. If the number of white and black impulse in the window are "x" and "y", respectively, we have better calculate " $P_{(N-x)}(i,j) - P_{(1+y)}(i,j)$ " edge signal instead of " $P_{(N)}(i,j) - P_{(1)}(i,j)$ ". Thus, in order to eliminate the effect of impulse noises for Max.-Min. method, it is necessary to estimate of the number of impulse noise in the window.

$$I^{(x)}_{\max}(i,j) = P^{(N)}(i,j) - P^{(N-x)}(i,j) \dots(2)$$

$$I^{(y)}_{\min}(i,j) = P^{(1+y)}(i,j) - P^{(1)}(i,j) \dots(3)$$

(x=1,2,...X y=1,2,...Y)

We can predict the number of white and black impulse in the window by using $I^{(x)}_{\max}(i,j)$ and $I^{(y)}_{\min}(i,j)$, respectively. For example, if two white impulse noises are exist in the window, $I^{(1)}_{\max}(i,j)$ shows small value and $I^{(2)}_{\max}(i,j)$ shows large value. In order to estimate the number of white and black impulse noise in the window, we introduce two modules of fuzzy rules(see Table 1) RM1(x) and RM2(y), respectively.

Table 1 Fuzzy rules of estimation the number of impulse noise

<p>RM1(x) :</p> <p>If $I^{(1)}_{\max}(i,j)$ is Small and $I^{(2)}_{\max}(i,j)$ is Small and $I^{(x-1)}_{\max}(i,j)$ is Small and $I^{(x)}_{\max}(i,j)$ is Large</p>
<p>RM2(y) :</p> <p>If $I^{(1)}_{\min}(i,j)$ is Small and $I^{(2)}_{\min}(i,j)$ is Small and $I^{(y-1)}_{\min}(i,j)$ is Small and $I^{(y)}_{\min}(i,j)$ is Large</p>

Thus, the number of impulse noise in the windows are estimated by the following fuzzy rules constructed by RM1(x) and RM2(y).

RM1(1)and RM2(1) then { (1,1) impulses in the window }
 RM1(1)and RM2(2) then { (1,2) impulses in the window }

 RM1(X)and RM2(Y) then { (X,Y) impulses in the window }
 else RM1(1) then { (1,0) impulses in the window }

 RM1(X) then { (X,0) impulses in the window }
 RM2(1) then { (0,1) impulses in the window }

 RM2(Y) then { (0,Y) impulses in the window }
 else { (0,0) impulses in the window }

where (x,y)=(the number of white impulse, the number of black impulse). The degree of

activation of the IF-THEN rules and Else rules are represented $\mu_{(x,y)}$

2.3 Combination of the edge detection and Gaussian noise attenuation

Gaussian noise is effectively removed by average filtering. However, average filtering also degrades the image edges and details. In order to compatible edge preservation and noise attenuation, we detect edge signal by subtracting the average of min. part from max. part and change the number of averaging pixel depend on the shape of local data (i.e., edge or background). We can estimate the shape of the image in local window by using the coefficient $K_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ [4] given by :

$$K_{(x,y)}(i,j) = \max\{(\sigma^2_{(x,y)} - \sigma^2_{(n)})/\sigma^2_{(x,y)}, 0\} \dots(4)$$

where $\sigma^2_{(x,y)}$ is the variance of local data except top x pixels and the bottom y pixels ($P^{(1+y)}, \dots, P^{(N-x)}$), so we can know the shape of local data except the effect of (x,y)impulse noise. $\sigma^2_{(n)}$ is the variance of Gaussian noise. Here, $K_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ is a local variance, and the value 0~1. So, if the window located background then the value becomes 0, and if the window located edge then value becomes 1. Thus, according to the following fuzzy rules, we can attenuate Gaussian noise and detect edge at the same time.

If $K_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ is Small then $E_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ is $E^{(S)}_{(x,y)}(i,j)$
 If $K_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ is Medium then $E_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ is $E^{(M)}_{(x,y)}(i,j)$
 If $K_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ is Large then $E_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ is $E^{(L)}_{(x,y)}(i,j)$

Where $E^{(L)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) = P^{(N-x)}(i,j) - P^{(1+y)}(i,j)$ and
 $E^{(M)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) = \left\{ \sum_{|l|=(N-x+y)/2}^{N-x} 2P_{(il)}(i,j)/(N-x-y) \right\} - \left\{ \sum_{|l|=ly}^{(N-x+y)/2} 2P_{(il)}(i,j)/(N-x-y) \right\}$

(i.e., Averaging with (N-x-y)/2 pixels)
 $E^{(S)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) = 0$ (i.e., Averaging with N-x-y pixels).
 Then edge signal $E_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ is derived by

$$E_{(x,y)}(i,j) = \frac{\lambda^{(S)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) \cdot E^{(S)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) + \lambda^{(M)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) \cdot E^{(M)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) + \lambda^{(L)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) \cdot E^{(L)}_{(x,y)}(i,j)}{(\lambda^{(S)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) + \lambda^{(M)}_{(x,y)}(i,j) + \lambda^{(L)}_{(x,y)}(i,j))} \dots(5)$$

where $\lambda^{(S)}_{(x,y)}(i,j)$, $\lambda^{(M)}_{(x,y)}(i,j)$, $\lambda^{(L)}_{(x,y)}(i,j)$ are the value of membership functions (see Fig.1(b)) of "Small", "Medium" and "Large", respectively.

(a) Membership function for fuzzy rules of section 2.1 (b) Membership function for fuzzy rules of section 2.2

Fig.1 Membership functions

2.4 The edge detection from images corrupted by mixed noise

number of impulse noise is estimated by the fuzzy rules in section 2.1, and edge detection and Gaussian noise attenuation are combined by the fuzzy rules in section 2.2 on the condition that the number of impulse noise is known. Thus, the signal edge $E(i,j)$ can be derived correctly, if we combine the results of two sets of rules, as follows :

$$E(i,j) = \frac{\sum_{x=1}^{X-1} \sum_{y=1}^{Y-1} E_{(x,y)}(i,j) \cdot \mu_{(x,y)} + \sum_{x=1}^{X-1} E_{(x,0)}(i,j) \cdot \mu_{(x,0)} + \sum_{y=1}^{Y-1} E_{(0,y)}(i,j) \cdot \mu_{(0,y)} + E_{(0,0)}(i,j) \cdot \mu_{(0,0)}}{(\sum_{x=1}^{X-1} \sum_{y=1}^{Y-1} \mu_{(x,y)} + \sum_{x=1}^{X-1} \mu_{(x,0)} + \sum_{y=1}^{Y-1} \mu_{(0,y)} + \mu_{(0,0)})} \quad \dots(6)$$

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Tuning of fuzzy sets

From Fig.1, the membership functions of $I(i,j)$ and $K(i,j)$ are defined by parameters (A,B) and (α, β) respectively. We try determining the optimal membership function experimentally by using image "Lenna" (256×256 pixels, 256 levels). We evaluate the edge detection performance by the E_s and N_e are given by :

$$E_s = \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in R_e} (s(i,j) - y(i,j))^2}{M \times \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^K s(i,j)^2} \quad \dots(7)$$

$$N_e = \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in R_b} (s(i,j) - y(i,j))^2}{(K-M) \times \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^K s(i,j)^2} \quad \dots(8)$$

where $s(i,j)$ means ideal edge image and $y(i,j)$ is edge image from arbitrary edge detector. R_e and R_b are edge and background regions, respectively. We evaluate the edge detection property by E_s and the noise attenuation property by N_e . The adequate membership functions are determined by comparing the method of the Max.-Min. method after 5point median filtering. The performance of both E_s and N_e are shown in Fig.2, and various (α, β) are shown in Fig.3. From these figures, we determine the optimal parameters as $(A,B)=(15,60)$ and $(\alpha, \beta)=(0,0.5)$.

Fig.2 The tuning of the parameters A and B

Fig.3 The tuning of the parameters α and β

3.2 Results of application

Computer simulations have been carried out to compare the performance of the proposed method with the method of (5point median filtering and the Max.-Min. method). An image called "Lighthouse" (see Fig.4) is also used in the simulations. The parameters of the membership functions are set as $(A,B)=(15,60)$, $(\alpha, \beta)=(0,0.5)$, according to the results of 3.1.

Fig. 4 Image “Lighthouse”

Fig. 5 Noisy Image

The original image corrupted by impulse noise with probability(4%) and zero mean Gaussian noise with standard deviation $\sigma_{(n)}=14$ are use for simulation(see Fig.5). Visual quality can be observed in Fig.6(a),(b). It is clear that proposed method is effective about preserving image details, even if processing except tuning image. It is natural result that the process of only edge detection can't reduce noise as Fig. 6(c),(d). E_s and N_e of the proposed method and the comparison method (i.e., 5point median filtering and the Max.-Min. method) are shown in Table 2. From this results, the proposed method was understood that not depend on images.

(a) Proposed method

$E_s = 0.265$
 $N_e = 3.55$

(b) Median + Max—Min. method

$E_s = 0.302$
 $N_e = 4.28$

(c) Sobel method

$E_s = 0.518$
 $N_e = 19.36$

(d) Differential method

$E_s = 0.280$
 $N_e = 13.53$

Fig.6 The results of edge detection

Table 2 The results of edge detection

(Gaussian noise : $\sigma^2=200$ + Impulse 4%)

Image		Proposed Method	Median + Max.-Min.
		E_s	
Lighthouse	E_s	0.265	0.302
	N_e	3.55	4.28
Teftef	E_s	0.339	0.496
	N_e	4.21	5.42
Lenna	E_s	0.270	0.355
	N_e	4.27	5.03
Building	E_s	0.298	0.397
	N_e	3.95	4.78
Boat	E_s	0.279	0.332
	N_e	3.84	4.76

4. CONCLUSIONS

this paper, a new edge detection using fuzzy technique is proposed, for the purpose of extracting details and edges from images that corrupted by mixed noise. Noise attenuation and edge detection are combined by using fuzzy technique. The tuning of fuzzy sets are relative easy, because of the robustness of fuzzy system. We think this practical edge detection was in this paper.

5. REFERENCES

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